

Echoes of the Subalterns in Amitav Ghosh's *River of Smoke*

**Dr. Dipika Bhatt,
Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
H.V.M. (P.G.) College,
Raisi, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.**

Abstract: *Amitav Ghosh's River of Smoke from the perspective of post-colonialism my paper proposes to examine and explore the problem of racial and cultural identity of subalterns. The main plot of River of Smoke is set in Fanqui town, situated on a small piece of land used by merchants from other countries to transact business with local Chinese traders. The novel's story begins before one year of Opium trade. In this novel Ghosh has created a rich and colorful cast of characters drawn from diverse geographical, cultural and historical backgrounds whose common interest is to make money by doing trade with China. The novel's plot is set in Fanqui town, situated on a small piece of land used by merchants from other countries to transact business with local Chinese traders. When the story begins the time is a year before of the first opium war. In River of Smoke Ghosh highlights on the issue of racial hybridity and culture through his subaltern characters. Bahram is a man of steely integrity. He married to a Parsi woman and son-in-law of a established merchant but imagined himself a successful businessman of his own empire. He thinks that the export trade between Western India and China was growing very fast, and offered all kinds of opportunities - not just of profit but also of travel, escape and excitement. Mr. Bahram Modi a Parsi man and Chi-mei a Chinese woman have an illegal son Ah Fatt. Ghosh wants to explore that in lack of good education and other essential facilities the boat children's development would not possible and they entered in the world of crime easily.*

He meets Dai-Lou, a big opium-sailor and he joined him. Ah Fatt told to Neel that Dia-Lou had many boys like him to work for him; he likes to hire his kind. Thus through the character of Bahram we find the male psyche of freedom and existence. Through my paper I highlight the problems and the poor condition faced by subalterns like Chi-mei, Ah Fatt and Adeline who sometimes for money, in lack of education and unawareness about rights suffer a lot in their life.

Keywords: Subaltern, Hybridity of race, Cultural hybridity, Lack of education and unawareness about rights, Opium trade

Ghosh's Ibis trilogy consists of three novels namely *Sea of Poppies*, *River of Smoke* and *Flood of Fire*. All these three novels are beautifully picturises some historical incidents like opium war and trade as settings. Ghosh made a ship called Ibis as a microcosm of culture in which people from different nations, cultures and castes were forced to intermingle with each other, ignorant about their future destination. Ibis trilogy is a story set in the first half of the 19th century. It speaks about the opium war and trade and trafficking of coolies to Mauritius. The first volume of Ibis trilogy, *Sea of Poppies* speaks about the stories of Deeti, an ordinary village woman of higher caste and her husband Hukum Singh, an opium addict worker in Gazhipur opium factory. Here Ghosh picturises Deeti, one of the central characters in the novel as marginalized woman because being a woman and a wife of an opium addict. Throughout the novel the reader can analyse the emotional pangs she was forced to withstand. At first she was seduced by her husband's brother, when she was unconscious then she was forced to attain sati from which she narrowly escapes with the help of Kalua, a down trodden man of low caste.

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local Chinese traders. The novel's story begins before one year of Opium trade. In this novel Ghosh has created a rich and colorful cast of characters drawn from diverse geographical, cultural and historical backgrounds whose common interest is to make money by doing trade with China. The novel's plot is set in Fanqui town, situated on a small piece of land used by merchants from other countries to transact business with local Chinese traders. When the story begins the time is a year before of the first opium war.

At the opening of the novel three ships namely Redruth, Anahita and Ibis from *Sea of Poppies*- run into a raging storm off the coast of Canton, the Chinese port city. The ship, Anahita is owned by Bahram Moddie who is a son-in-law of Rustamji Mistris, a Parsi Opium trader of Bombay. The other ship, Redruth is owned by Fitcher Penrose who is on an expedition to collect rare species of plants from China, and the last ship, Ibis, is carrying convicts and indentured labourers to Mauritius. In *River of Smoke*, Ghosh highlights on the issue of racial hybridity and culture through his subaltern characters.

Once there had been a time when Bahram's own family had also been prosperous and well-respected, occupying a place of distinction in their hometown of Navsari, in coastal Gujarat; his grandfather had been a well-known textile dealer, with important court connections in princely capitals like Baroda, Indore and Gwalior. But in his waning years, after a life time of prudence, he had made a slew of rash investments, incurring an enormous burden of debt.

Being a man of steely integrity, he had taken it upon himself to pay off every loan, down to the last tinny, coproon and half anna; as a result, the family had been reduced to utter penury, with no more than a handful of cowries in their khazana. Forced to sell off their beautiful old haveli, they had moved into a couple of rooms on the edge of town, and this had proved fatal for the old man as well as his son, Bahram's father, who was a consumptive and had suffered

from lifelong ill health; he did not live to see Bahram's navjote - his ceremonial induction into the Zoroastrian faith.

His mother was an exceptionally good needlewoman, and the shawls she embroidered were much prized and admired. When word of the family's plight spread through the community, orders came pouring in, and by dint of thrift and hard work, she was able not only to feed her children, but also to provide Bahram with the rudiments of an education. In time her renown spread as far as Bombay, fetching her important commission: she was asked to supply embroidered wedding shawls for the daughter of one of the foremost Parsi businessmen of the city - Seth Rustamjee Pestonjee Mistris. The two families were not unknown to each other, for the Mistris business had also been founded in Navsari - its origins lay in a small furniture work shop which the Modis', in their heyday, had lavishly patronized and supported. Attached to the workshop was a shed for building boats: although small to begin with, this part of the business had quickly outstripped very other branch. After winning a major contract from the East India Company, the Mistris' had moved to Bombay where they had opened a shipyard in the dockside district of Mazagon. On taking charge of the firm, Seth Rustamjee had built energetically upon his inheritance, and under his direction the Mistris shipyard had become one of the most successful enterprises in the Indian subcontinent. Now, his daughter was to marry a scion of one of the richest merchant families in the land, the Dadi seths' of Colaba, and the wedding was to be celebrated on a scale never seen before.

But a few days before the beginning of the festivities, with all the arrangements made and anticipation at its height, fate intervened: one of the Dadi seths' associates in Aden had presented the prospective bridegroom with a fine Arab stallion, and the boy who was only fifteen had insisted on taking it for a ride on the beach. Disoriented after the long journey across the sea, the horse was sorely out of temper: galloping headlong on the sand, the boy was thrown and killed. For the Mistris family the boy's death was a double disaster: not only did they lose the son-in-law of their

dreams, they had also to reconcile themselves to the knowledge that the tragedy would make it difficult, if not impossible, for their daughter to make a good marriage: her prospects were sure to be contaminated by the stain of misfortune.

When they began to send out feelers once again, their apprehensions were quickly confirmed: the girl's plight occasioned much sympathy without eliciting any acceptable offers of marriage. When it became clear that no proposals would be forthcoming from within their circle, the Mistris reluctantly took their search beyond the city, to their ancestral town, where they presently found their way to Bahram's mother's door.

After facing many difficulties this branch of the Modis was acknowledged to be of respectable pedigree, and Bahram himself was a sturdy, good-looking lad, more-or-less educated, and of an appropriate age, being almost sixteen years old. Hearing good reports of him, the Seth met with Bahram during a trip to Navsari and was favorably impressed by his eagerness and energy: it was he who decided that the boy would be an acceptable match for his daughter, despite the disadvantages of a rough-edged demeanour and a poverty-stricken upbringing. By Mistris the proposal that was sent to Bahram's mother was qualified by certain stipulations that since the boy had no money and no immediate prospects for advancement, the couple would have to live in Bombay, in the Mistris mansion, and the groom would have to enter the family business. Here Indian's belief on fate and astrology is truly picturised.

Bahram's mother who had facing many difficulties in her life says that "For a man to live with his in-laws, as a 'house-husband' - a gherjamai - is never an easy thing. You know what people say about sons-in-law: kutra pos, bilarā pos per jemeinājeniyānevarmākhos - rear a dog, rear a cat, but shove the son-in-law and his offspring into the gutter..." (*River of Smoke* 48). He knew that an opportunity like this one was unlikely ever to be presented to him again and he accepts his offer.

Bahram and Shireenbai moved into an apartment in the Mistrie mansion on Bombay's Apollo Street. Shireenbai was a shy, retiring girl whose spirits had been permanently dimmed by the tragedy that preceded her marriage; her demeanour was more of a widow than a bride, and she seemed always to be shrouded in melancholy, as though she were mourning the husband she should have had. Towards Bahram she was dutiful, if unenthusiastic, and since he had not expected much more, they dealt with each other well enough and had two daughters in quick succession.

Mistries had succeeded in making their firm into a formidable force within a fiercely competitive industry because they had kept their attention closely fixed upon their chosen fields of expertise. To fit into such a specialized organization required, of a newcomer, certain skills and abilities that Bahram did not possess: tools did not sit well in his fidgety hands, details bored him, and he was too individualistic to stay in step with a team of fellow workers. His tenure as an apprentice shipwright was a short one and he was quickly shunted off to a dingy daftar at the back, where the firm's accounts were tabulated.

But this suited him no better for neither numbers nor the men who worked with them were of the least interest to him: shroffs and ledger-keepers seemed to him to be painfully constrained in their vision of the world, devoid of imagination and entrepreneurship. His own gifts, as he saw them, were of a completely different kind; he was good at dealing with people, staying abreast of the news, and was blessed moreover with a sharp eye for sizing up risks and opportunities: not for him the tedium of coin-sifting and column-filling - even while serving time in the daftar, he was careful to keep himself informed of other openings, never doubting that he would one day chance upon a field of enterprise that was better suited to his talents. He thinks that the export trade between Western India and China was growing very fast, and offered all kinds of opportunities - not just of profit but also of travel, escape and excitement. But he knew that to persuade the Mistrie's to enter

this arena would not be easy; in matters of business they were deeply conservative and disapproved of anything that smacked of speculation. When Bahram first brought up the matter of entering the export trade, his father-in-law had reacted with distaste: “What? Selling opium overseas? That’s just gambling - it isn’t something that a firm like the Mistries’ can get involved in “(*River of Smoke* 51).

He told to his father-in-law today the biggest profits don’t come from selling useful things: quite the opposite. The profits come from selling things that are not of any real use. Look at this new kind of white sugar that people are bringing from China - this thing they call ‘cheeni’.

Is it any sweeter than honey or palm-jaggery? No, but people pay twice as much for it or even more. Look at all the money that people are making from selling rum and gin. Are these any better than our own toddy and wine and sharaab? No, but people want them. Opium is just like that. It is completely useless unless you’re sick, but still people want it. And it is such a thing that once people start using it they can’t stop; the market just gets larger and larger. That is why the British are trying to take over the trade and keep it to themselves (*River of Smoke* 51).

He said to his father-in-law fortunately in the Bombay Presidency they have not succeeded in turning it into a monopoly, so there is no harm in making some money from it. Every other shipyard maintains a small fleet, to engage in overseas trade; maybe it is time for the Mistrie’s to set up an export division of their own. Look at the returns that some other firms are getting of late, by exporting cotton and opium: they have been doubling and even tripling their investments with every consignment they send to China. If he gives him permission he will be glad to make an exploratory voyage to Canton. After much discussion his father-in-

law allowed Bahram to go to China. For him, of all the surprises of that journey, none was greater than that of the foreign enclave of Canton, where the traders resided.

‘Fanqui-town’, as old hands called it, was a place at once strangely straitened yet wildly luxurious; a place where you were always watched and yet were free from the frowning scrutiny of your family; a place where the female presence was strictly forbidden, but where women would enter your life in ways that were utterly unexpected: it was thus that Bahram, while still in his twenties, found himself gloriously and accidentally entangled with Chi-mei, a boat-woman who gave him a son - a child who was all the more dear to him because his existence could never be acknowledged in Bombay (*River of Smoke* 52).

Mr. Bahram Modi a Parsi man and Chi-mei a Chinese woman have an illegal son Ah Fatt. Ah Fatt a half-Chinese boy lived in Canton found out in his boyhood that he had connections, relatives, in faraway Bombay. As a child he had been told that he was an orphan that his mother and father had died when he was a newborn, and that he was being brought up by his widowed Eldest Aunt Chi-mei - his Yee Ma. This was the story that was told to everyone who knew them, on the Canton waterfront and in Fanqui-town. Mr. Bahram Modi whom they called Uncle Barry, his Kai-Yeh had been his father’s employer and after his parents’ death he had felt a great obligation to their orphaned child; this was the reason that he gave Yee Ma money for his upkeep, and brought presents for him from India, and paid for his teachers and tutors. We should take cognizance of Ah Fatt’s other name Freddy as this signifies the duality of his identity. Ah Fatt is rarely used by Bahram Moddie; he always calls him Freddy, a non-Chinese name. Ah Fatt’s real identity was based on the area he was born in. In China he was called by his Chinese name - Ah Fatt and in India and some other places he was called Freddy and Fremji Moddie.

Yee Ma did not encourage Uncle Barry's ambitions for the boy: she did not approve of spending so much money on such things. To arrange schooling for a boat-child was no easy matter and Uncle Barry had to pay generously to organize it: he wanted the boy to be literate in Classical Chinese as well as schoolroom English; he wanted him to grow up respectable, to become a gentleman, who would be able to move easily with the merchants of Fanqui-town, impressing them with his sporting talents as well as his knowledge. Yee Ma could not see the point of all this: she would have preferred that Uncle Barry give her the money and leave the boy alone. She thinks;

What use was calligraphy to him when boat-people were banned by law from sitting for the Civil Service examinations? What was he to do with boxing and riding lessons when boat-people were barred even from building houses ashore? She wanted him to grow up like any boat-child, learning to fish and sail and handle boats (*River of Smoke* 89).

Here Ghosh wants to explore that in lack of good education and other essential facilities the boat children's development would not possible and they entered in the world of crime easily. Yee Ma in her dreams if not in her waking state must have accepted that he was not really a boat-child for she often had nightmares in which the boy was attacked by a dragon-fish - a sturgeon. As a result she would not let him in the water. Like other boat-children Ah Fatt grew up with a bell attached to his ankle, so his family could always keep track of him; like them he had to sit in a barrel when the boat was moving; like them, he had a wooden board tied to his back, so that he would float if he fell in. But the other children lost their boards and bells when they were two or three - Ah Fatt's stayed on till long afterwards, making him a target of mockery. On the Canton waterfront little boys would earn money by diving in the river to amuse the Aliens, fishing out the coins and trinkets they threw in the water. Ah Fatt too wanted to do these things, to swim with the boat-children, to dive and earn coins - but to him

alone, these things were strictly forbidden because of the spectre of the lurking dragon-fish.

Ah Fatt told to Neel that the pun-tei i.e. the land-people mocks us and say we have fins instead of feet. Sometimes Ah Fatt also goes to dive for coins with others when Yee Ma was not there. Then one day she find out, and she pull him from the water. Beat him, shaming in front of everyone. So much shame, he think throw him in the river, and if dragon-fish comes, that is also good.

“I think: she doing this because I have no parents. I think: if I her child, she not beat like this. I think: better run away. I make plans, I speak with beggar-men, but Older Sister find out. Then she tells me everything: that Yee Ma not aunt, but Mother. That ‘Uncle Barry’ not kai-yeh, but Father” (*River of Smoke* 90).

Next time when Mr. Barry come Ah Fatt asked to him was this true that he was his father and Yee Ma was mother? At first, he said no this was not true but finally he said that yes, all was true and he has other family in Bombay. Ah Fatt was very shocked by this incident. He said to Neel that;

When I small, we live in boat like this one; we also poor people, like these. Just poor boat-people, sometime no food, we eat wind. Then one day I hear my father hou-gwai, rich man, rich White-Hat Devil. Now I think I know why my mother beat me - I not real China-yan, I her secret shame, but still she need me, because of money Father gives. I read in books that “Western Island” -India have gold and magic and I want to go - I want fly there like Monkey King. But this is in my head my feet in kitchen-boat where I live. So when I hear of Father’s ship, Anahita, I am mad to see it (*River of Smoke* 90).

After seeing Anhita a luxurious ship of his father Ah Fatt became very anxious and wants to know more about India. Ah Fatt left his

family in Canton and went to Lintin Island in fast-crab. There he meets Dai-Lou, a big opium-sailor and he joined him. Ah Fatt told to Neel that Dia-Lou had many boys like him to work for him; he likes to hire his kind i.e.:

Jaahp-júng-jai-‘mixed-kind-boy’. Many like that along Pearl River -in Macau, Whampoa, and Guangzhou. In any port, any place where man can buy woman, there is many yeh-jai and ‘West-ocean-child’. They too must eat and live. Dai Lou give us work, treat us well. For long time he like real Elder Brother to me. But then we have trouble (*River of Smoke* 92).

So he had to left Canton and run away. Dai-Lou have a woman not wife but a concubine. She was very beautiful. Her name was Adeline. Adeline was also salt prawn-food like me: she was also half Cheeni and half Achha (Hindustani). He said that Achha means good or all right but it is opposite in Gwong-jou-talk. Here Ah-cha means bad man. Her mother was from Goa but lives in Macau. Her father was Chinese, from Canton. Adeline was very attractive; she also likes smoke opium. When Dai Lou travels, he tells him to look after Adeline. Sometime she asks to him bite the cloud with her. “We both half-Achha, but never seen India. We talk about India, about her mother, my father. And then...” (*River of Smoke* 93).

They became lovers and his boss found out. Just like countries have laws, gaa have rules. He knows Dai Lou try to kill him so he hides with mother. Then he hears hing-dai come for him, so he runs away. Go to Macau, and pretend to be Christian, hide in seminary. Then they send him to Serampore, in Bengal and Adelina killed herself.

This is the tragic story of two persons who were deprived of their family’s love and care comes to an end. Here the true picture of racial hybridity is clear. The illicit romance between Bahram Modi and Chi-mei is strong enough to challenge ethnic, linguistic and

cultural barriers; the only image that comes to his mind while he is endangered is that of Chi-mei rather than his lawful wife and daughters. This “lob-pidgin” (*River of Smoke* 74) love story seems to prove that language and culture prove no strong barriers as far as human bonding is concerned.

Thus through the character of Bahram we find the male psyche of freedom and existence. Bahram an imaginative, freedom lover, entrepreneur soul, wants his own identity and establish himself as a businessman who transport traders to the opium market place with the ship Anhita. He was married and had two daughters but for fulfilling his motives he started as the owner of a new business of opium traders who transport opium during post-colonial era. During his visit to China Bahram had illicit relationship with Chi Mee and had a son from this relation named Ah Fatt. Through my paper I highlight the problems and the poor condition faced by subalterns like Chi-mei, Ah Fatt and Adeline who sometimes for money, in lack of education and unawareness about rights suffer a lot in their life.

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